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The relationship of online resource use and academic writing of students

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Abstract: Online resources have become the trend in terms of making references accessible to students. The relevance of which has been indispensable with innovations in technology. This research was initiated to determine the relationship between online resource utilization and academic writing. The study employed a correlation method that involved 61 students. Results show that Online resource utilization was very high. In addition, the academic writing of students was high. It was also observed that a significant relationship between Online resource utilization and academic writing exists.

Keywords: Online resource utilization, academic writing, student development

1. RATIONALE:

Academic writing has been part of the academic pursuit for students. Regardless if it is basic education and tertiary education. The curriculum was designed to inculcate written communication as part of the learning outcomes of students. It was reported that academic writing to be difficult for non-native English speakers. It was even suggested that academic institutions should devise different writing styles for various subjects. These included; summaries, research papers, and other reports [1].

Previous studies have documented the use innovative technology. From using Learning Management System, Youtube, Asynchronous Learning Tools. [2-4] However using innovative technology does not mean that students are adept in searching for references. A study in an Australian university described several difficulties of a student's academic writing experience. It was found out that the most challenging part of the academic writing included the use of library computer databases for proper referencing. This even included the components that came after resource utilization such as: deciding on the most significant elements for the write up as well as combining ideas from various sources [5].

A case study performed at De La Salle University Manila (DLSU) revealed advantages in the incorporation of technology in class. Employing interactive learning environments enhanced course delivery. This is evident in the usage of the internet to disseminate the

student' output. Teachers who handle writing classes employed publishing capabilities of the internet. This allowed students to gain a better knowledge of proper referencing. [6].

The researchers observed that was no local study that investigated the relationship of online resource utilization and the academic writing of students. Given that no study has been conducted corelative online resource utilization and academic writing. This stirred the researchers to pursue the study in the local context.

2. METHOD

Research Design

This study is quantitative by nature. More specifically, the research design observed was a quantitative non-experimental model. This was selected by the researchers since the research involved a statistical relationship of two variables [7]. The study is correlational by nature because it involved the relationship of two variables. The variables being Online resource utilization and Academic writing. The study had 61 students from the Department of Arts and Sciences. The study complied with the suggested sample size suggested of at least 30 or more for correlational studies [8]. In fact, this has been observed by other studies which are correlational by nature [9-10]

3. RESULTS OR FINDING

Table 1 shows the results of the online resources utilization of students. The descriptive level was observed to Very High garnering an overall mean for online resources utilization of 4.32. This means that the online resource utilization is prevalently practiced by students. This can be attributed to students very high usage of the internet [11]. The results imply that use of online resource for various reasons is performed by students.

It was also observed that each specific indicator of online resources utilization all garnered a descriptive level of very High. From the three indicators, E-books got the highest mean of 4.48. This is followed by Software with a mean score of 4.27 while Scholarly Journals got a mean score of 4.21. The results show that student's usage of E-books is the most prevalent as compared to Scholarly Journals and Software. This can be attributed to the popularity of E-book as a learning material [12]. Furthermore, Scholarly Journals which also got a descriptive level of very high. Scholarly Journals are also expanding significantly due to awareness among the users about the library e-resources and services, and its availability [13].

Table 1. Online Resources Utilization

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive level
E- Books	4.48	0.43	Very High
Scholarly Journals	4.21	0.64	Very High
Software	4.27	0.53	Very High
Overall	4.32	0.44	Very High

Utilization of Software was also described as very high. Using software has become mainstream in terms of storing and using references. The use of different software can be attributed to the students' acceptance and comfortability [14-15]. This allow students to make use of different features that can result to the development in the academic writing of student [16].

Table 2. Academic Writing

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive level
Grammar	4.04	0.46	High
Language Proficiency	4.41	0.45	Very High
Structure	3.97	0.47	High
Overall	4.14	0.39	High

Table 2 shows the mean score of Academic writing. It is observed that the overall mean is 4.41. This has a descriptive level of high. This high level can be attributed to all indicators garnering either very high or high level as a descriptive level. This means that the Academic Writing in terms of Grammar, Language Proficiency and Structure is very much manifested by the students.

From the three indicators of Academic writing, it was found that Language Proficiency garnered the highest mean of 4.41. This suggests that students are inclined to focus on language proficiency as a competency in academic writing. This includes emphasis not only on the specialized vocabulary of the content areas, but also patterns of grammatical and discourse variance for Academic languages in various correspondences. This even includes scholarly works in research and instruction [17]. Grammar and Structure both got mean scores described as High, with corresponding means scores of 4.04 and 3.97. This suggests that grammar and structure have been highly regarded in academic writing. Learners understand that both are valuable tools for deductive reasoning. Both grammar and structure have evident and implicit functions in organizing intellectual thoughts. In fact, people learn to create strong arguments though learning grammar structure. This concept was illustrated with lesson plan examples that demonstrate distinctions in the English language permits students to "analyze and criticize statements that use this distinction implicitly" while considering grammar constructs that help them better express themselves and understand the English language [18].

Table 3. Relationship between Online Resources and Academic Writing

Variable	r-value	p-value
Online Resources	0.500*	0.001
Academic Writing		
*p < 0.05		

Table 3 shows the result of the relationship between Online Resources and Academic Writing of students. Results show the computed p -value of 0.001 and an r-value of 0.500. Given that the p-value is lesser than 0.05, this means that a significant relationship between the variables exist. Thus, Online resource utilization affects the Academic writing of students. This result is supported by another study that explored the relationship between college students' writing and the pedagogical use of online resources. The study validates that there a positive relationship between the variables. If students can use the information gained through online resources, they can actively engage in written discourse. The study also finds that utilizing internet resources is critical to directly enhance student academic writing [19].

4. CONCLUSION

Results of the study became the basis for the following conclusions. (1) The students are accustomed to the use of online resources as evidenced in the very high utilization across three platforms: e-books, scholarly journals and software. (2) The students also demonstrated high levels of Academic writing and finally (3) Online resource utilization has a significant relationship with Academic writing. In line with the following results, teachers should integrate online resources in teaching students most especially under topics that fall under academic writing. Teachers must continuously adapt to meet the needs of the students. The use of technology is no longer detached from education. As technology evolves so does educational trends. Teachers can integrate online resources in their teaching to keep up with the trend of education today. Further studies can also be explored for both online resources and academic writing. Future researchers may look into studies on online resource utilization using other methodologies to further contribute to the existing knowledge.

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